

Urban Heat Island - ZGZ-UHI

To identify the Urban Heat Islands, the University of Zaragoza collects data from two different sources:

- 1) Air temperature measured by a network of 21 thermo-hygrometric sensors placed around the city.
- 2) Satellite, vegetation, digital surface and other type of data from national and international geospatial initiatives. These will be used to explain the distribution of the temperature in the city (in the Calving method).

Use case goal: This use case is focused on the identification of the Urban Heat Islands in the city of Zaragoza, using data from a network of sensors of the city and also satellite public data that is collected from national and international geospatial initiatives. This data will be used as a decision ready data that will allow decision makers to establish policies. This step is performed by the University of Zaragoza.

In addition, the municipality wants to publish this data in their open data portal and in their visualization service in order to disseminate this knowledge and information to the citizen.

